

Usability

How easily and effectively people can accomplish their goals using a product or system, while having a positive experience.

Usability refers to the measurement of how easily a user can accomplish their goals when using a service. This is usually measured through established research methodologies under the term “usability testing,” which includes success rates and customer satisfaction. Usability is one part of the larger user experience (UX) umbrella. While UX encompasses designing the overall experience of a product, usability focuses on the mechanics of making sure products work as well as possible for the user.

RELATED POLICY

**21st Century Integrated Digital Experience Act and
OMB M-23-22**

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FEATURED RESOURCE

Human-Centered Design Guide Series

A series of guides to help you understand and practice human-centered design.

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Create better user-centered products for the public.

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Best practices for creating clear, useful, digital content for federal websites and digital services.

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A resource with four approaches to help federal employees perform usability testing.

[Usability Testing with Steve Krug](#)

Get started making usability fixes to your website or product.

[18F Methods](#)

A collection of tools that describe how teams can put human-centered design into practice.

[Usability Starter Kit](#)

Here are some tools and templates to help you create better user experiences.

Usability events

USWDS

USWDS Monthly Call - January 2025

Learn the U.S. Web Design System basics, how to get started with the design system, and what's coming next for USWDS in 2025.

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USWDS

USWDS Monthly Call - December 2024

The U.S. Web Design System team is joined by the Federal Website Standards team to share more about the standards, their origin, the research backing them, and what standards are coming next.

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The U.S. Web Design System (USWDS) team will share their vision for the design system as a product, including USWDS Web Components and other new things the team expects to deliver in 2025.

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The U.S. Web Design System team will share the product and engineering principles they're using to

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guide the development of the design system.

event_organizer: Digital.gov

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Spring 2024 Community Summit

Digital service experts across the federal government will share case studies and best practices on delivering a digital-first public experience.

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Usability news

Navigating digital acquisitions

Learn the best practices for agile acquisitions — from building and buying solutions, to overcoming common roadblocks.

[Frances Carden](#)

[Ashley Owens](#)

Nov 26, 2024

Enhancing the customer-centricity of GSA websites

An overview of GSA’s website evaluation process, which combines qualitative and quantitative data to assess website management and performance.

[Behati Hart](#)

Oct 30, 2024

Making targeted improvements to NPS.gov: A case study from the National Park Service

NPS enhances user experience on NPS.gov by integrating Digital Analytics Program web analytics data and customer feedback from GSA Touchpoints.

 [Nathan King](#)

Oct 11, 2024

Uncovering impactful solutions through user research

Get an overview of what user research and user testing are in a federal context. Learn what policies apply and what resources are available.

 [Frances Carden](#)

Oct 4, 2024

Developing an easier way to recruit user research participants

USA.gov and 10x recently partnered to develop a new user research recruitment page. The page launched in February 2024 and has attracted hundreds of sign-ups. It allows participants to assist in testing government websites for compensation, and helps teams find participants that match needed demographics. By simplifying the process and expanding recruitment of diverse populations, the initiative aims to support and streamline user research. It plans to add recruitment opportunities in additional languages and recruit more specific audiences for future studies.

— via [USA.gov](https://www.usa.gov)

Aug 6, 2024

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More News and Events on Usability

59 posts

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— via [USA.gov](#)

Aug 6, 2024

Designing for people with disabilities

The User Experience (UX) team at USA.gov's Public Experience Portfolio recently conducted a study to analyze the experiences of individuals who access USA.gov through assistive technology. The team partnered with a local organization to gather insights from a diverse group of participants, many of whom are blind or deaf. The study revealed various habits and challenges faced by these users, such as a preference for mobile sites, difficulty with website carousels, and a reliance on clear headings and action-oriented descriptions. These findings can guide improvements in accessibility, such as clever link labeling and better navigation aids for assistive technology users.

— via [USA.gov](#)

Jul 16, 2024

A small team's journey through digital maturity

As a small team, Digital.gov adopted user research and customer experience early. That foundation helps develop evidence-based strategies for today.

 [Sarah Schroeder](#)

Jul 8, 2024

Case study: Removing barriers to applying for a presidential pardon

At the Department of Justice, Access DOJ and the Office of the Pardon Attorney (PARDON) partnered to simplify and streamline the presidential pardon application process. By conducting usability testing and gathering feedback, they identified key issues with the existing application, such as its complexity and length. See how redesigning the forms to be more accessible and understandable led to a more efficient process for both applicants and staff.

— via [Department of Justice](#)

Jun 6, 2024

One year with the new USA.gov

It has been a year since USA.gov and USAGov en Español were relaunched using human-centered design principles. Using task backlog, the USAGov team has addressed content gaps, improved discoverability, and implemented technical updates. Through usability tests, visitor comments, and click behavior the team was able to unravel and respond to user feedback and unmet needs, leading to noticeable increases in visitor satisfaction and task accomplishment. Moving forward, the focus will shift to enhancing public engagement with the government, improving the search for benefits-related content, and exploring interactive and personalized user experiences.

— via [USA.gov](#)

May 14, 2024

Determining the true value of a website: A

GSA case study

GSA has developed a composite indicator to visualize six key components of website success.

[Ana Monroe](#)

[Aaron Meyers](#)

Apr 16, 2024

18F at ten

We're celebrating all the ways we continue to realize our founding vision: bringing technologists into government, launching shared digital services, and helping partner agencies build user-centered technology.

— via [18F](#)

Mar 19, 2024

Search.gov year in review: 2023 report

Learn what types of information people searched for on federal websites in 2023, see emerging trends the team is exploring to improve customers' search experience in 2024, and check out three new updates. The data tab provides insightful summaries for 13 popular topic areas — and lists the public's top 25 search terms, in their own words, for each.

— via [Search.gov](#)

Mar 15, 2024

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Spring 2024 Community Summit

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Timeless top 10 best practices for great government websites

While the field of federal web management continues to evolve, the core best practices have remained essentially unchanged for two decades.

[Ammie Farraj Feijoo](#)

[Rachel Flagg](#)

Feb 9, 2024

Accessibility testing: Creating digital services everyone can use

Making sure that USA.gov and USAGov en Español remain accessible to people with disabilities is essential. The product team shares four testing tips they've learned to help ensure that everyone has equal access to digital products and services.

— via [USA.gov](#)

Jan 9, 2024

5 things we learned from our scams wizard usability test

USAGov's usability (UX) team developed a step-by-step process for visitors to easily report a scam. Here are 5 things the team learned from performing usability testing on the tool.

— via [USA.gov](#)

Oct 4, 2023

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